

INGLIZ TILIDAGI “FAMILY”- “OILA” QADRIYAT KONSEPTINING LEKSIK-SEMANTIK TAHLILI

*Nizamova Salomat Usmanovna,
Oriental universiteti, Tillar - 2 kafedrasida katta o‘qituvchisi*

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada “family-oila” giperkonsepti sifatidagi qadriyat tushunchasi tilini, uning xususiyatlari va ushbu qadriyat tushunchasini tashkil etuvchi mezonlarini o‘rganishga bag‘ishlangan. Belgilangan vazifalarni hal qilish uchun lingvistik materialni tahlil qilish algoritmini ishlab chiqish zarur bo‘lib tuyuladi, bu esa ingliz tilidagi “family-oila” qadriyat konseptining amal qilishining pragma-semantik va lingvomadaniy parametrlarini to‘liq tushunishga imkon beradi. Dominant qadriyatlarni aniqlash maqsadida amerikalik mualliflar tomonidan badiiy adabiyot matnlari asosida oilaviy qadriyatlarning til vakillarining pragma-semantik, kognitiv-semantik tahlili – “family-oila” konseptining semantik ko‘lamini tashkil etuvchi asosiy mezonlar tahlil qilindi.

Kalit so‘zlar: *dwelling, salbiy munosabat, ijobiy munosabat, yashirin munosabat, qadriyat, relations, oilaviy munosabatlari, qarindoshlik munosabatlari, children, farzandlarga munosabat.*

Abstract. This article is devoted to the study of the language of the concept of value as a hyperconcept “family”, its features and the criteria that form this concept of value. To solve the specified tasks, it is necessary to develop an algorithm for analyzing linguistic material, which will allow us to fully understand the pragmatic-semantic and linguocultural parameters of the functioning of the concept of value “family” in the English language. In order to identify dominant values, American authors conducted a pragmatic-semantic, cognitive-semantic analysis of linguistic representatives of family values based on literary texts - the main criteria that form the semantic scope of the concept of “family”.

Keywords: *dwelling, negative attitude, positive attitude, hidden attitude, value, relations, family relations, kinship relations, children, attitude to children.*

“Family-oila” qadriyatlari konseptining tizimlashtirish va uning konseptual sohasining asosiy xususiyatlarini tavsiflash katta ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Avvalgi maqolamizda biz britan *Oxford Learner’s Dictionary* va *Amerika Merriam Webster’s Dictionary* lug‘atlari ta’riflarining tahlili “family-oila” leksemasining asosiy/yadroli ma’nolarini aniqlash imkonini berdi. Mazkur maqolada oilaviy qadriyatlar va “family-oila” qadriyatlari konseptining barcha to‘plangan misollarini tahlil qilish va ularning leksik-semantik tasnifini ko‘rsatib berish rejalashtirilgan. Badiiy asarlar matnlaridan foydalangan holda bunday tahlil qilish uchun asos bo‘lib, birinchi navbatda, “family-oila” so‘zining ma’lum kontekstlar doirasida amalga oshiriladigan asosiy ma’nolari va shu bilan o‘rganilayotgan “family-oila” konseptining mazmuni ochib bershga harakat qildik.

Tadqiqot materiali sifatida turli semantik tarkibga ega bo'lgan ushbu konseptning qadriyat-semantik maydoni bilan bog'liq "family-oila" yoki oilaviy qadriyatlar konseptining ob'ektivlashuvi kontekstlari hisoblanadi.

"Family-oila" va boshqa konseptlarning leksik-semantik, pragma-semantik, kognativ-mazmuniy va boshqa yo'nalishlari bo'yicha yetarli darajada ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda. Masalan, rus tilshunoslari N.N. Goncharova, Yu.A.Iksanova, V.I. Krasik, M.M.Kovalevskiy, V.A.Maslova, I.A.Zyuzina, D.G. Larionova, N.Yu. Kazakova, Z.A. Axmetjanova, V.B. Tyurin, N.V. Nagovitsina, A.N.Pribilova, M.Yu.Romanyuk, M.V.Zimina kabi ilmiy tadqiqotchilar rus, nemis, fransuz, ingliz, ispan, edigey, tatar va boshqa tillardagi maqollarda "family"-oila" konseptining turli yo'nalishlarini o'z ishlarida ochib berganlar.

O'zbek tilshunosligida ham konsept masalasiga doir turli ishlar, ya'ni Z.I.Salieva, A.M. Bazarbaeva, K.M. Amanullaeva, Sh.Q. Shamsieva, N.B. Kuldosheva, D.K. Baxronova, Z.R. Gulyamova, Yu.T. Nosirov va boshqalarning ilmiy tadqiqot ishlari amalga oshirilgan, turli konseptlar, turli yo'nalishlarda tadqiq etilgan. Biroq aynan va "family"-oila" konsepti o'zbek lingvistikasida alohida tadqiqot darajasida o'rganilmagan.

Ushbu maqolada yetakchi tadqiqot usullari sifatida, ta'rifiy, qiyosiy, tavsifiy, uzluksiz tanlab olish usuli, konseptual tahlil usuli, lingvokulturologik usul va lug'at ta'riflarini tahlil qilish metodlari qo'llanildi. Pragma-semantik va kognitiv tahlil uchun kontekst sifatida XX –XXI - asrlarda yozilgan quyidagi badiiy janrdagi adabiyotlar – Loren Vaysbergerning "Prada kiygan iblis", Daniel Stilning "Baxt" ("Dadajon"), Nikolas Sparksning "So'nggi qo'shiq" kabilar tanlab olindi.

Loren Vaysbergerning "Prada kiygan iblis", Daniel Stilning "Baxt" ("Dadajon"), Nikolas Sparksning "So'nggi qo'shiq" asarlarda yozuvchilar oilaning ahamiyati va oilaning bosh qahramonlar hayotidagi o'rni kabi oilaviy qadriyatlar masalasini ko'taradilar.

"Family-oila" giperkonseptining qadriyat toifalarining lingvistik tasvirlarini to'plash uchun ishlatiladigan barcha san'at asarlarining qahramonlari Amerika til madaniyati vakillari bo'lganligi sababli, ularning oilaviy qadriyatlari boshqa xalqlar olamining qadriyat manzarasida taqdim etilgan qadriyatlardan sezilarli darajada farq qilishi mumkin.

Barcha toifalar lingvistik talqin shaklida taqdim etilgan qadriyat xususiyatlari va belgilari nuqtai nazaridan ko'rib chiqiladi.

Avvalo, "family-oila" leksemasining ta'rifiy tahlil natijasida olingan asosiy belgilarini aks ettiruvchi kontekstlarni ko'rib chiqamiz.

Shunday qilib, **birinchi guruhni** family tushunchasining *dwelling* ma'nosidagi "muayyan munosabatlar bilan birlashgan odamlar guruhi tomonidan umumiy bo'lgan uy, xonadon, boshqa yashash joyi" sifatida ifodalanishidagi misollar tashkil etadi.

(1) *It took four weeks for me to feel human again and another two until I began to feel that **living at home was unbearable**. Mom and Dad were great, but being*

*asked where I was going every time I left the house—or where I'd been every time I returned—got old quickly*¹.

Ushbu misol (1) Lauren Vaysbergerning “Prada kiygan iblis” kitobidan olingan bo‘lib, qahramon ayol otasining uyini tark etib, endi yaqin o‘tmishni eslaydi. Kontekstdan biz bosh qahramonning “uy” haqidagi tushunchasi oilasi “*Mom and Dad*” bilan bog‘liqligini bilib olamiz. Biroq, “*unbearable*” sifatdoshi va “*got old quickly*” iborasi tufayli qahramonning uyga nisbatan munosabati juda salbiy ekanligini tushunish mumkin, bu tushunarli, chunki balog‘atga etgan ko‘plab odamlar, shu o‘rinda qahramon ayol ham uydan imkon qadar tezroq chiqib ketishga va mustaqil kattalar hayotini boshlashga intilgan.

(2) *She lived in Purchase, New York, in a beautiful house they almost owned, after fourteen years of struggling with the mortgage. She had three children, one dog, the last hamster had finally died the year before. And she had a husband she loved*².

Daniel Stilning “Baxt” (“Dadajon”) asaridagi misolda (2) butunlay boshqacha manzarani kuzatish mumkin. Bizning oldimizda qariyb 20 yildan beri turmush qurgan qahramon ayol turadi. Bu misolda “uy” leksemasiga “*beautiful*” deb ijobiy baho berilgan. “*Fourteen years of struggling with the mortgage*” so‘zlarida egalik qilish uchun uzoq kutilgan uyning qadriyati aniq ifodalangan. Bundan tashqari, kontekstda biz “family-oila” leksemasining boshqa yadro ma’nolarini – “children”, “relations” (“*three children*”, “*a husband she loved*”) ham kuzatamiz.

(3) *She wasn't just visiting her dad. Visiting implied a weekend or two, maybe even a week. She supposed she could live with a visit. But to stay until late August? Pretty much the entire summer? That was banishment...*³.

Nikolas Sparksning “So‘nggi qo‘shiq” kitobidan olingan misol (3) ham tadqiqot uchun qiziqarlidir. Bu yerda onasi bilan ajrashgan otasining uyiga yozni o‘tkazish uchun borgan o‘smir qiz qahramon haqida so‘z ketadi. Ushbu misolda *dwelling* ma’nosi yashirin bo‘lib, u qahramonning otasi bilan “qolishi” kerakligini “*banishment*” ga ishora deb hisoblaydi. Bolalar va ota o‘rtasidagi yomon munosabatlar bilvosita aks ettirilgan, shuning uchun qahramonning otasi yashaydigan joy ham salbiy baholanadi. Shunga qaramay, boshqa “children”, “relations” kabi yadroviy ma’nolar bilan o‘zaro ta’sir kuzatiladi.

Ikkinchi guruh *relations* – oilaviy munosabatlar, yaqin munosabatlar, qon qarindoshlik munosabatlarini amalga oshiradigan misollar bilan ifodalanadi.

(4) “... *Marriage is for women who are looking for someone to support them. I want to take care of myself, Oliver Watson*”.

(5) *In the eighteen years they'd been married, she'd become so dependent on him. He took care of all the little problems in her life, and most of the big ones. It was like living in a hermetically sealed world, with Ollie always there to protect her*⁴.

¹ Weisberger L. The Devil Wears Prada.- 2003. (Электрон ресурс, мурожаат санаси 09.03.2025).

² Steel D. Daddy.- DELL PUBLISHING, 2010. – URL: file:///C:/Users/Win/Downloads/steel_danielle_daddy.pdf (Мурожаат санаси 09.03.2025)

³ Sparks N.- The Last Song.- Great Britain: Sphere, 2010. (Электрон ресурс, мурожаат санаси 09.03.2025).

⁴ Steel D. Daddy.- DELL PUBLISHING, 2010. – URL: file:///C:/Users/Win/Downloads/steel_danielle_daddy.pdf (Мурожаат санаси 09.03.2025).

Misollarda (4, 5) qahramon turmushga chiqish sabablarini tasvirlaydi. Bu nikoh qahramonning ochilishiga yo‘l qo‘ymaydi, chunki 20 yil davomida bu turmush uni eriga qaram qilib qo‘yadi (“*she’d become so dependent on him*”) va buni “*in a hermetically sealed world*” taqqoslash tasdiqlaydi. Bu yerda oilaviy munosabatlar juda salbiy tasvirlangan. Ikki bir-biriga zid holat, ya’ni asardagi holatda bo‘lgani kabi nikoh har doim boshqa oila a’zosini qo‘llab-quvvatlash bilan bog‘liq, lekin qahramon ayol erkinlikni/mustaqillikni orzu qiladi.

(6) *Okay, she wasn’t the worst mom. She really wasn’t. And when she was feeling generous, Ronnie might even admit that she was pretty good as far as moms went. < ... > and Ronnie wished for the hundredth time that she’d been born in May instead of August. That was **when she’d turn eighteen, and her mom wouldn’t be able to force her to do anything. Legally, she’d be old enough to make her own decisions...***¹

Misolda (6) bizga oilaviy va qarindoshlik munosabatlari taqdim etiladi. Bu yerda biz bolalar va ularning ota-onalari o‘rtasidagi tushunmovchilik asosidagi avlodlar to‘qnashuvini kuzatishimiz mumkin, asosiy qahramon nazoratdan charchagan “*to force*” (bosim o‘tkazish) va erkinlikka, mustaqillikka “*old enough to make her own decision*” intilish g‘oyasi aniq ifodalangan.

Yuqorida tahlil qilingan misolida (1) biz avlodlar to‘qnashuvini, ota-onalarning haddan tashqari nazoratini ham kuzatamiz: *Mom and Dad were great, but being asked where I was going every time I left the house—or where I’d been every time I returned—got old quickly.*

Shunday qilib, uchta misoldan foydalanib, biz ikki turdagi – qarindoshlik va yaqin munosabatlarni tahlil qildik. Shulardan kelib chiqqan holda biz bu munosabatlarni ko‘pincha salbiy baholash mumkin, degan xulosaga kelishimiz mumkin, lekin ularda ijobiy holatlar (qo‘llab-quvvatlash, nazorat) ham mavjud.

Uchinchi guruhga asosiy “children”- farzandlar ma’nosini ifodalovchi misollar kiradi.

Daniel Stilning “Baxt” (“Dadajon”) asarida farzandlar mavzusi aniq ko‘rsatilgan bo‘lib, bosh qahramon va qahramon ayolning farzandlarga bo‘lgan munosabati juda farq qiladi.

(7) *“Is that what Oliver feels too?” She didn’t answer for a long moment. She didn’t want to tell him that **Ollie had always wanted more children. He was doing well, advancing rapidly in the firm, and even if they had been starving, he wouldn’t have let her get an abortion. He just wouldn’t. It was their baby. Theirs. And long before the baby came, he loved it***².

Misollar (7, 8) bosh qahramonning farzandlariga bo‘lgan mehri ko‘rsatilib, bunday mehr uning xotinida bo‘lmaydi. Albatta, bu misol real hayotda tez-tez uchramaydi, lekin, ayniqsa, turmush o‘rtoqlar o‘rtasida tenglik mavjud bo‘lgan Amerika mentalitetida bunday holat kam bo‘lsada mavjud. Bundan tashqari, “*It was their baby. Theirs*” jumllarida egalik olmoshining takrorlanishi nafaqat bosh

¹ Sparks N.- The Last Song.- Great Britain: Sphere, 2010. . (Электрон ресурс, мурожаат санаси 09.03.2025).

² Steel D. Daddy.- DELL PUBLISHING, 2010. – URL: file:///C:/Users/Win/Downloads/steel_danielle_daddy.pdf (Мурожаат санаси 09.03.2025).

qahramon uchun farzandlarning muhimligini bildiradi, balki farzandlar u uchun oilaviy hayotining bir qismi hisoblanadi.

(8) <...> *he walked around the house, carrying him in his arms, while Sarah collapsed in a chair with a sigh and a glass of wine, wondering how she was going to survive it. Motherhood was definitely not her strong suit, and the apartment was so small, it was driving her crazy*¹.

Misolda (9) ko‘rinib turibdiki, “collapse”, “survive” fe‘llarida onalik bosh qahramon uchun katta quvonch olib kelmaydi shuningdek, “drive one’s crazy” iborasi mazkur kontekstda keskin muhitini yaratadi.

“So‘nggi qo‘shiq” asarida otalik mehrining quyidagi misollarda ko‘rsatishimiz mumkin.

(9) *He fell asleep almost immediately but woke an hour later. Tiptoeing outside again, he went to check on **the daughter he loved more than life itself**.*

(10) *Steve **loved his children more than life itself**, but more than that, he knew that Jonah needed him, and once more, he was struck by the realization that he was failing as a father*².

Misoldagi (10, 11) “more than life itself” taqqoslash farzandlarni “hayotning o‘zidan ko‘ra ko‘proq” sevadigan qahramonning dunyoqarashidagi qadr-qimmatni ko‘rsatadi.

(11) *Even though it didn’t work out in the end the way you or I wanted it to, I see you and Jonah and I think **how lucky I am to have you as children**. In a lifetime of mistakes, **you two are the greatest things that have ever happened to me**”³. Misoldagi (12) “lucky”, “the greatest” ijobiy sifatlari farzandlarga bo‘lgan muhabbatni namoyish etadi va ularning hayotdagi ahamiyatini tushunishga imkon beradi.*

Leksik-semantik tahlil jarayonida “family-oila” leksemasining asosiy ma’nolarining amalga oshirilishi ham ijobiy, ham salbiy bo‘lish belgilarini aniqladik, bu esa o‘z o‘rnida, ma’lum kontekst doirasida o‘zini namoyon qiluvchi “family-oila” leksemasi tarkibidagi baholovchi komponentning mavjudligini ko‘rsatadi.

Demak, “family-oila” leksemasining ta’rifiy tahlili natijasida ochilgan o‘zak ma’nolari badiiy asar matnlarida keltirilgan lisoniy tasvirlar bilan ham tasdiqlanadi. Asosiy ma’nolar bir xil kontekstda paydo bo‘lishi, o‘zaro ta’sir qilishi yoki bir-birini to‘ldirishi, boshqa qadriyatlarni inkor etishi yoki ma’lum bir baholash komponenti mavjudligi sababli ustunlik qiluvchi asosiy qahramonlar olami manzarasida qadriyat sifatida ishlashi mumkin. Shuning uchun asosiy qadriyatlarni “family-oila” konseptining qadriyat-semantik ko‘lamining asosiy tarkibiy qismlari sifatida ko‘rish mumkin.

Shunday qilib, *dwelling* ma’nosini amalga oshirish doirasida biz “home”ni “family-oila”ning qadriyat konsepti bilan bog‘liq tarkibiy komponent sifatida ajratib ko‘rsatishimiz mumkin, *relations* ma’nosi er-xotin yoki oilaviy munosabatlar –

¹ Steel D. Daddy.- DELL PUBLISHING, 2010. – URL: file:///C:/Users/Win/Downloads/steel_danielle_daddy.pdf (Мурожаат санаси 09.03.2025).

² Sparks N.- The Last Song.- Great Britain: Sphere, 2010. (Электрон ресурс, мурожаат санаси 09.03.2025).

³ Ўша ерда.

relatives o'rtasidagi munosabatlarda ifodalanadi, children ma'nosi ham "family-oila" qadriyat konseptining tarkibiy elementi sifatida qaralishi mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Steel D. Daddy.- DELL PUBLISHING, 2010. – URL: file:///C:/Users/Win/Downloads/steel_danielle_daddy.pdf (Murojaat sanasi 09.03.2025).
2. Sparks N.- The Last Song.- Great Britain: Sphere, 2010. (Elektron resurs, murojaat sanasi 09.03.2025).
3. Weisberger L. The Devil Wears Prada.- 2003. (Elektron resurs, murojaat sanasi 09.03.2025).